

The Hustle by the Overpass; An Observational Study of the Activities of “Side Mates” at KNUST's Tech Junction

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Tech Junction, a major entry point to the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), is a bustling hub of activity where one can find a diverse group of individuals, including students, traders, and a unique breed of entrepreneurs that I call "side mates." During my two-day observation of Tech Junction, I witnessed a dynamic display of resourcefulness and hustle among the bustling crowds. Unlike official conductors, these young men operate from the sidelines, shouting out destinations and assisting drivers in the hopes of earning a small tip when the bus reaches full capacity. They move quickly from place to place, always on the lookout for potential customers and their desired locations.

The emergence of these "side mates" is a response to the harsh economic realities of the country¹. They play a vital role in the public transport system² and fill the gap left by official conductors who primarily manage passengers within the bus. Acting as extensions, these "side mates" use their improvisational skills to attract and secure potential customers from a wider pool. However, this often leads to disagreements with the original conductors (popularly known as mates) who claim "ownership" of the passengers, highlighting the intense competition for limited income and the desperation for every cedi earned. Despite receiving relatively small amounts, usually between GHC 1 and GHC 5 per bus fill, these young men have found a way to support themselves in the absence of formal employment opportunities³. They have formed a symbiotic relationship with official conductors, working together to ensure the smooth operation of the transport system.

¹ De Soto, H. (1989). *The other path: The informal sector in Latin America*. Harper & Row.

² Brubaker, G., & Moser, G. (2004). *The informal economy: Its role in development*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³ World Bank. (2020). *Informal sector employment in Sub-Saharan Africa*. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/798701601482469323/pdf/A-Tale-of-Africa-Today-Balancing-the-Lives-and-Livelihoods-of-Informal-Workers-During-the-COVID-19-Pandemic.pdf>

Although this relationship is not without its challenges, fueled by the shared struggle for survival⁴, it remains an integral part of the public transport ecosystem.

The presence of the "side mates" highlights the adaptability and entrepreneurial spirit that is prevalent in Ghanaian society⁵. They have identified a need within an existing system and capitalized on it to earn a living⁶. This improvisational approach, while sometimes disruptive, is a testament to the ingenuity and resilience of ordinary people navigating economic uncertainties.

Their activities provide a fascinating insight into the multifaceted realities of life in contemporary Ghana⁷. Their story is of economic hardship⁸, entrepreneurial spirit⁹, and the constant negotiation of informal structures within a formal system. As Ghana grapples with economic challenges, these "side mates" contribute to the vibrant tapestry of life at KNUST in their unique way, reminding us of the resourcefulness and resilience that can blossom even in the harshest of environments.

⁴ Agyemang, A. (2020). *Hustling for survival: The everyday lives of young people in Accra, Ghana*. University of California Press.

⁵ Gyamfi, Y. (2018). Entrepreneurial activity in Ghana: An overview. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Studies*, 2(1), 1-14.

⁶ Ansell, P. (2012). The social origins of the informal economy: A framework for analysis. *International Journal of the Commons*, 6(1), 1-20.

⁷ Agyemang, A. (2020). *Hustling for survival: The everyday lives of young people in Accra, Ghana*. University of California Press.

⁸ World Bank. (2023). Ghana: Overview. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/ghana>

⁹ Adjasi, C. K. (2017). The informal sector in Ghana: A critical analysis. *Journal of Pan African Studies*, 11(1), 1-14.

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